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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH ON CLASSIFICATION OF
SPLEEN AND LIVER INJURIES DUE TO BLUNT ABDOMINAL
TRAUMA WITH RESPECT TO GENDER & AGE****Dr. Hafiza Madeeha Latif, Dr. Maria Ghaffoor, Dr. Rabbia Bajwa**
Allied Hospital Faisalabad**Abstract:**

Objective: Objective of our research was to determine the grading of spleen and liver injury frequencies on exploratory laparotomy after the blunt trauma of abdomen.

Methods: Our cross-sectional was carried out Service Hospital, Lahore (August 2016 to March 2017). We included all those cases who had a history of blunt trauma of abdomen, intraabdominal haemorrhage, hemodynamic instability (Pulse rate above 100 beats per minute and systolic BP under 90 mmHg) and about to experience exploratory laparotomy. Both male and female patients were included in the research in the age bracket of (16 – 50) years. We did not include non-operative, penetrating injury of abdomen, stampede and natural disaster injured cases with those who were not willing to participate in the research. Informed consent and ethical approval were taken before the commencement of research. Data was analyzed on SPSS.

Results: Research sample consisted of 183 blunt trauma of abdomen cases with a mean age of (31.05 ± 9.25) years. In the total sample, 136 males (74.3%) and 47 females (25.7%) were included. Spleen and Liver injuries were reported in 121 and 96 with respective proportions of (66.1%) and (52.5%). Liver injury cases were classified in Grade I, II, III, IV and V with the respective proportion of 38 G-I (20.8%), 29 G-II (15.8%), 24 G-III (13.1%), 3 G-IV (1.6%) and 2 G-V (1.1%) cases. Spleen injury cases were also classified in Grade I, II, III, IV and V with the respective proportion of 40 G-I (21.9%), 24 G-II (13.1%), 27 G-III (14.8%), 24 G-IV (13.1%) and 6 G-V (3.3%) cases.

Conclusion: the Most repeated abdominal injury was blunt trauma. Young males were dominantly affected than females. Most commonly injured organ was spleen in the blunt trauma patients than liver. Splenic injuries were mostly graded as Grade I & III.

Keywords: Focused Assessment, Blunt Abdominal Trauma, Trauma Sonography, Mortality, Computed Tomography and Diagnostic Peritoneal Lavage.

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INTRODUCTION:

An exchange of environmental energy that is more than the resilience of the human body is called trauma [1]. Society is facing the burden of deaths caused by trauma even in the advanced strategies of disease management. People under the age of fifty years face mortality and morbidity all over the world which is also increasing the disease management costs [2]. The abdomen is a large surfaced area which is affected most of all due to injuries [4]. Spleen and Liver are common organs affected by abdominal blunt trauma along with hemoperitoneum in the second and third decade of life [10]. Abdominal blunt trauma cases experiencing laparotomy were reported Liver and Spleen injuries respectively in 47.9% and 61.7% of cases [3]. Liver injuries were mostly found in Grade I, II & III having a respective proportion of 42.8%, 28.35% and 22.85% [4]. Spleen injuries were also reported in Grade I, II, III, IV and V respectively as 31.34%, 19.40%, 23.88%, 20.90% and 4.48% [13]. After the incidence of Spleen and Liver blunt injuries, the rate of mortality was as high as (12%) [4].

The weight of the abdomen is about 1500 grams, which makes it the largest organ and its location is in the abdomen right upper part under diaphragm which is guarded by ribs [5]. The blunt injury was the major cause of liver injuries because of the solid shape of the Liver and compression force applied to it from ribs can burst the liver [6]. Location of Spleen is in between stomach and diaphragm in the guard of rib number nine to eleven [7]. Spleen injuries are caused because of a direct trauma blunt as the force is directly exerted on the mentioned ribs [6]. A rib fracture is forty percent linked with liver injury and twenty-three percent with spleen injury [8]. Emergency operations required for intra-abdominal injuries are high in case of six ribs are damaged which is reported about 51% [9].

It is important to define Liver and Spleen injuries in order to assess and understand the effects of these injuries on the patients. We can associate Liver and Spleen injuries with hematoma, exploratory laparotomy bleeding or wound observed on Liver and Spleen surface area as classified by the American Trauma Surgery Association [1, 4]. SPSS was used for data entry and analysis. Quantitative and qualitative variables were calculated for outcome representation. Gender and age stratification was also carried out to control the effect of the modifiers. Variables effect was also assessed by Chi-Square Test ($P \leq 0.05$).

RESULTS:

The research sample consisted of 183 blunt trauma of abdomen cases with a mean age of (31.05 ± 9.25) years. In the total sample, 136 males (74.3%) and 47 females (25.7%) were included. Spleen and Liver injuries were reported in 121 and 96 with respective proportions of (66.1%) and (52.5%). Liver injury cases were classified in Grade I, II, III, IV and V with the respective proportion of 38 G-I (20.8%), 29 G-II (15.8%), 24 G-III (13.1%), 3 G-IV (1.6%) and 2 G-V (1.1%) cases. Spleen injury cases were also classified in Grade I, II, III, IV and V with the respective proportion of 40 G-I (21.9%), 24 G-II (13.1%), 27 G-III (14.8%), 24 G-IV (13.1%) and 6 G-V (3.3%) cases. Liver injuries were mostly found in Grade I, II & III having respective proportion of 42.8%, 28.35% and 22.85%. Spleen injuries were also reported in Grade I, II, III, IV and V respectively as 31.34%, 19.40%, 23.88%, 20.90% and 4.48%. After the incidence of Spleen and Liver blunt injuries, the rate of mortality was as high as (12%). There was no significant correlation between age groups about the injuries with a significant P-value as 0.64. We also found no correlation between gender and age in terms of outcomes as reflected in the tabular data. There was also no significant association in the gender about Spleen injury.

Table – I: Blunt Trauma, Liver and Spleen Injury

Details		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	136	74.3
	Female	47	25.7
	Total	183	100
Age Group (Years)	17 - 33	113	61.7
	34 - 49	70	38.3
	Total	183	100
Injury of Liver	Yes	96	52.5
	No	87	47.5
	Total	183	100
Spleen Injury	Yes	121	66.1
	No	62	33.9
	Total	183	100

Table – II: Liver and Spleen Injury Distribution

Age and Gender Distribution			Age Group (Years)			Gender		
			17 - 33	34 - 49	Total	Male	Female	Total
Liver Injury	Yes	N	61	35	96	73	23	96
		%	54	50	52.5	53.7	49	52.5
	No	N	52	35	87	63	24	87
		%	46	50	47.5	46.3	51	47.5
	Total	N	113	7	183	136	47	183
		%	61.7	38.3	100	74.3	25.7	100
Spleen Injury	Yes	N	76	45	121	93	28	121
		%	67.3	64.3	66.12	68.4	60	66.12
	No	N	37	25	62	43	19	62
		%	32.7	35.7	33.88	31.6	40	33.88
	Total	N	113	70	183	136	47	183
		%	61.7	38.3	100	74.3	25.7	100
P-Value			0.64, 0.74			0.61, 0.28		

DISCUSSION:

All age groups are affected by the injuries of blunt trauma of abdomen [10]. Serious pathology of intra-abdomen is sometimes very difficult and challenging. The initial assessment may fail in the manifestation of injuries in the course of treatment. Injury mechanisms may pose other associated injuries which may pose a threat to the life of the patients [11]. Most frequent injuries of blunt trauma are caused by the motor-cycle accidents, vehicle accident, assaults, pedestrians struck and falls [17]. A physical assessment will not suffice the need of diagnosis, various modalities are used for the diagnosis of the injuries such as laparoscopy, ultrasonography and CT scans. Abdominal exploration is required in 25% of trauma patients [12]. Males were dominantly affected than females as 74.3% of the males were involved in the blunt trauma cases which can be compared with the outcomes of Gad MA et al. [13]. The maximum occurrence was reported in the age group of (17 – 33) years which is treated as Group – I in this research and Group – II was a second most affected group with an age bracket of (34 – 49) years. Maximum incidence reporting in the age bracket of (20 – 29) years was reported by Frick EJ et al.; whereas, Mufti reported the age of 27 years [14, 15].

Trauma injuries were reported in 52.5% of the patients which is comparable with the outcomes as

reported by Mohamed AA and Memon respectively 47.9% and 53.12% [3, 16]. Raza reported 13.2% liver injury cases with the maximum trend of Grade – III cases (58.8%) which is also comparable with our research [17]. Liver injury incidence was reported about 28.57% by Aman [18]. Liver injury grading was also reported by Saaq in his research as Grade I, II, III and IV were respectively reported as 32.7%, 36.2%, 25.6% and 6.1% [19].

A common onset of blunt trauma was commonly reported in the age bracket of (17 – 33) years about (61.7%). M Swarnkar reported 64.06% cases of abdomen blunt trauma in the age group of (11 – 40) year, which is almost the same as our outcomes [20]. Spleen is a very vulnerable organ for injuries even in the guard of ribs in almost every age group [1]. It is a vascular and friable organ which carried twenty-five percent of lymphoid tissue with both immunological and haematological functions [15]. We found 66.1% cases of spleen injury; whereas, Raza reported the same as 29.8% [17]. Najafi and Ghazanfar reported 18.5% & 23% cases of spleen injuries [21, 22]. Sample population may be the cause of varying outcomes. Renzulli P reported Spleen injury Grades I, II, III, IV and V with respective proportions of 20.9%, 25.2%, 29.1%, 20.4% and 4.4% [23]. Various reasons are responsible for the difference in the outcomes such as age group and a number of patients enrolled in the research.

CONCLUSIONS:

The most repeated abdominal injury was blunt trauma. Young males were dominantly affected than females. Most commonly injured organ was spleen in the blunt trauma patients than liver. Splenic injuries were mostly graded as Grade I & III.

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